

Anti-angiogenesis efficacy of the aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* and its combination with melatonin in an animal model: *in vivo* and *ex vivo* studies

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Abstract

To better understand *Allium sativum*'s anti-angiogenesis activity, we undertook this study to examine its effect on the *ex vivo* rat aortic ring and the *in vivo* chick chorioallantoic membrane. Additionally, we compare *Allium sativum*'s anti-angiogenesis activity to melatonin and study the benefits of their combination. The study included six albino male rats (aged 5–7 weeks). The rats were euthanized, and then the thoracic aorta was removed and cut into rings that were 1 mm thick. The study was divided into three groups: a negative control (1% v/v DMSO), a positive control (100 µg/mL melatonin), and an aqueous *Allium sativum* extract. The test compounds were subjected to serial dilutions to obtain 100, 50, 25, 12.25, and 6.25 µg/mL concentrations. In addition, the *in vivo* chick chorioallantoic membrane was also undertaken. *Allium sativum* and melatonin significantly inhibited the rat aorta ring; the IC₅₀ was calculated (IC₅₀ = 8.04 for *Allium sativum* and 3.313 for melatonin). The zone of inhibition for melatonin, *Allium sativum*, and the combination showed that the combination had the strongest effect on the CAM assay. This zone scored (++) and (+++), respectively. In conclusion, the aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* provides a potent anti-angiogenesis effect, and its combination with melatonin had a synergistic effect, further enhancing its anti-angiogenesis effect.

Keywords

garlic, melatonin, angiogenesis, combination

Introduction

Researchers and practitioners worldwide have been interested in compounds obtained from natural sources as nutraceuticals due to their efficacy, immediate accessibility, and safety (Chen et al. 2018). Nature possesses a diverse array of biologically active compounds, particularly in plants, enabling them to be proficient builders of synthetic chemicals; this presents a viable alternative to

combinatorial chemistry in the search for important therapeutic substances (Slusarenko et al. 2008). Contemporary medications often originate from the traditional medicine of several cultures. Medicinal plants are crucial in discovering new drugs through organized screening programs or by chance discoveries (Abu-Dahab and Afifi 2007).

Melatonin, an indoleamine hormone, is crucial in controlling humans' circadian rhythm. Additionally, its antioxidant activity has gained significant attention in

recent years (Li et al. 2023). Furthermore, melatonin is a powerful agent that effectively eliminates harmful free radicals and acts as an antioxidant specifically aimed at mitochondria. This action helps safeguard against oxidative stress and locally decreases the presence of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) (Cipolla-Neto and Amaral 2018; Abed et al. 2020; Aranarochana et al. 2021; Bashandy et al. 2021). In addition, melatonin and its metabolites provide protection to lipids, proteins, and DNA by preventing oxidative damage and nitrosative stress (Cipolla-Neto and Amaral 2018; Ibrahim et al. 2019; Yong et al. 2021). Melatonin has the ability to prevent cell death in some scenarios, such as in ischemia-reperfusion injuries. This type of injury involves harmful processes that cause damage through oxidative stress and the movement of white blood cells, as well as an inflammatory immunological response. In addition, melatonin has been utilized in several tissues to decrease the absorption of calcium by cells and regulate the production of antioxidants (Ferreira et al. 2016; Tamura et al. 2020). The effects of Melatonin extend beyond its role as an antioxidant that directly neutralizes free radicals. It indirectly stimulates the cellular antioxidant defense system by increasing levels of mRNA and glutathione reductase (GSH), as well as the activities of several antioxidant enzymes, including glutathione peroxidase (GPx), catalase (CAT), and superoxide dismutase (SOD), which converts O_2 into H_2O_2 (Taghizadieh et al. 2016; Olayaki et al. 2018; Bashandy et al. 2021). Assessing these enzymes helps confirm the antioxidant properties of melatonin in cells. Melatonin utilization has also been linked to reduced levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), which is the final product of lipid peroxidation and serves as an indirect signal of heightened intracellular formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Therefore, the utilization of melatonin results in a reduction in lipid and peroxidation levels, leading to a decrease in cell death (Aranarochana et al. 2021).

Garlic, scientifically known as *Allium sativum* L., is a vegetable crop that belongs to the Alliaceae family. It has shallow roots. *Allium* is a seasoned plant that originated in central Asia and is extensively found in the northern hemisphere's temperate, warm temperate, and boreal zones (Ammarellou et al. 2022). The primary attribute of garlic is the unique taste of its cloves, which arises from intricate biochemical interactions (Hughes et al. 2005). The primary constituents of garlic consist primarily of sulfur-containing, non-volatile amino acids known as thio-sulfonates. Alliin, or S-allyl-cysteine sulfoxide (ACSO), is the most abundant precursor of garlic flavor (Randle and Lancaster 2002). Furthermore, they can also enhance glutathione production, which plays a crucial role in antioxidant activities (Banerjee et al. 2003). Ajoenes are additional volatile chemicals that possess strong bioactive characteristics (Block et al. 1993). In addition to alliin, numerous other sulfur-containing compounds are present, including allicin, 1,2-vinyldithiin, and S-allyl-cysteine (Kopeck et al. 2013).

Research has demonstrated that garlic possesses chemicals with powerful anti-tumor, anti-microbial, and anti-mutagenic properties (Dorant et al. 1993). Allicin demonstrates antioxidant properties by inhibiting the oxidation of lipids in liver homogenate, mostly due to its ability to scavenge hydroxyl radicals (El-Saber Batiha et al. 2020). Cells possess various genes that encode various proteins to counteract the harmful effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Within the transcriptional control of these beneficial genes, antioxidant response elements (AREs) play a significant role (Raghunath et al. 2018). Compounds with inherent antioxidant characteristics can regulate ROS and mitigate their detrimental impact on cells. It is crucial to comprehend how these compounds modulate the signaling pathways involved in cancer development. Prior studies have demonstrated that several organosulfur compounds found in garlic can inhibit the cell cycle at either the G1 or G2/M phases in both cancerous and non-cancerous cells. Allicin demonstrated significant growth inhibition in mammary, colon, and endometrial cancer cells and other human fibroblast lines, but greater dosages were required (Hirsch et al. 2000; Taher et al. 2018).

To better understand the anti-angiogenesis activity of *Allium sativum*, we undertook this study to examine its effect on the ex vivo rat aortic ring and the in vivo chick chorioallantoic membrane. Additionally, we compare the anti-angiogenesis activity of *Allium sativum* to a well-known compound (melatonin) and study the benefits of their combination.

Methods

Plant material

This study utilized a water-based extract of garlic (*Allium sativum* L.; family Alliaceae). Garlic bulbs were acquired from the central market in Baghdad, Iraq (33°18'46.0980"N, 44°21'41.3568"E) and authenticated by a traditional Iraqi herbalist.

Aqueous bulb extract preparation

It was prepared as previously described by Mikail's study using a hot aqueous extraction procedure; 500 g of garlic bulbs that had been dried in the air were sliced into small pieces and crushed. The crushed garlic was immersed in distilled water at 100 °C for 30 minutes. Afterward, the liquid mixture underwent cooling and passed through Whatman's filter paper to eliminate the plant residue. The collected liquid was subjected to drying in an oven at a temperature of 40 °C for 12 h to increase the concentration of the sample. The crude extract, which was yellowish and crystalline, was employed in the experimental trials at a dose of 20 mg kg⁻¹ on the same day it was used to treat animals with garlic extract (Mikail 2009).

Study design and settings

The study included six albino male rats (aged 5–7 weeks). Before the start of the investigation, the rodents were acclimated for two weeks at the Al-Mustafa University College animal facility in Baghdad, Iraq. The animals were given a standardized pellet diet and unlimited access to water provided by the facility. The study was prepared following ARRIVE GUIDELINES 2.0.

The rats were euthanized using intraperitoneal (IP) anesthesia with a single dose of 80 mg/kg of ketamine and 10 mg/kg of xylazine. Following the administration of full anesthesia, the rats were euthanized using carbon dioxide (Underwood and Anthony 2020; Yaribeygi et al. 2023). The thoracic aorta was removed, washed with serum-free medium, cleared of any remaining periadventitial fibro-adipose tissue, and cut into rings that were 1 mm thick. The study was divided into three groups: a negative control (1% v/v DMSO), a positive control (100 µg/mL melatonin), and an aqueous *Allium sativum* extract.

The test compounds were subjected to serial dilutions to obtain 100, 50, 25, 12.25, and 6.25 µg/mL concentrations. The original stock samples were dissolved in DMSO and then diluted in the M199 growth medium to achieve a final DMSO content of 1%. Wells that did not have test samples were treated with a medium containing 1% DMSO, which was used as the negative control.

Ring aorta assay

The experiment was conducted using a 48-well tissue culture plate. Each well is supplemented with 300 µl of a solution containing 3 mg/mL of fibrinogen and 5 mg/mL of aprotinin in a serum-free medium [M199]. The ring tissue is positioned at the center of the well. Ten µl of thrombin is introduced to every well, produced at a concentration of 50 NIH U/mL in 0.15 M NaCl. The mixture was heated for 10 minutes at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator to make it solid and develop a fibrin gel. Ideally, the vessel fragment would remain suspended in the center of the gel.

Next, 0.3 ml of M199 media (aminocaproic acid at 0.1% concentration, gentamycin at 0.6% concentration, glutamine at 1% concentration, and heat-inactivated fetal bovine sera at 20% concentration). The test compounds were introduced into the growth media (100 µg/mL); the solution was created by mixing dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) with the materials introduced to M199 media with a final concentration of 1%. Subsequently, the culture plates were placed back into an incubator containing 5% carbon dioxide at room temperature for five days. On day four, the upper section of the media was removed, and fresh media was reintroduced.

The vessel growth was quantified manually using a camera and software package under a magnification of 40× on day 5. Nicosia's methodology assessed the extent of vessel proliferation suppression (Nicosia 2009). The data are reported as the average percentage of inhibition compared to the negative control, with the standard deviation (SD) included. The experiment was conducted three

times with six replicate samples. The following formula was used:

$$\text{Blood vessels inhibition (\%)} = 1 - \frac{A_0}{A} \times 100$$

Where A_0 is the length of vessel growth of the investigated compound (mm), and A is the length of vessel growth of DMSO (mm).

In vivo chick chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) assay

The experiment utilized fertilized chicken eggs obtained from Al-Mustafa University College. The eggs were incubated at 60% humidity at room temperature for three days. During incubation, the eggs were positioned horizontally. On the fourth day, a tiny hole is made, and a small amount of albumin (2–3 ml) is extracted and sealed; this is done to lower the embryo and the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) for better observation of the CAM formation and its separation from the eggshell. The eggs were subjected to incubation for an additional 24 h. A small square window measuring 3–4 cm was created on the shell on day 5. Test samples, soaked in round filter paper discs, were placed on the chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) through the window. The window was then covered with sterile surgical adhesive tape to maintain sterility and humidity. The eggs were subsequently incubated for an additional 72 h (Li et al. 2015).

Ultimately, the area of inhibition was captured through photography and quantified. The test samples, consisting of *Allium sativum*, melatonin, and a combination of both, were prepared at 10 mg/mL and 50 µl concentrations. The final dose of *Allium sativum* and melatonin was 0.5 mg per disc, while the final dose of the combination was 0.25 mg of each drug per disc (0.5 mg). These samples were applied to filter paper discs and allowed to dry before being transferred to the CAM. The entire process was conducted using sterile techniques (Lokman et al. 2012).

The responses will be evaluated as follows: + for responses measuring between 3 and 6 mm, ++ for responses measuring between 6 and 9 mm, and +++ for responses measuring greater than 10 mm. The zone of inhibition was quantified using an image analyzer (Martin and Murray 2009).

Combination index

The combination index of various combinations (constant ratio combinations) showed a combination index (CI) value between 0 and 1, which indicates a synergistic effect at all concentrations measured, as illustrated by Fig. 4. The following equation calculates CI (Chou 2006):

$$CI = \frac{D_1}{(D_m)_1 \left[\frac{f_a}{(1-f_a)} \right]^{m_1^{-1}}} + \frac{D_2}{(D_m)_2 \left[\frac{f_a}{(1-f_a)} \right]^{m_2^{-1}}}$$

CI is the combination index, D_1 is the concentration of Drug 1, D_2 is the concentration of Drug 2, D_m is the IC₅₀, and f_a is the fraction affected.

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the research ethical committee of Al-Mustafa University College (ID: AA006, date: 1 September 2023).

Statistical analysis

An independent t-test was used to compare the difference in mean between the groups; a p-value was considered significant if it was less than 0.05. All analyses were carried out using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.0. The IC₅₀ was determined using logarithmic calculations conducted by CompuSyn, Inc.

Results

Allium sativum and melatonin have a notable inhibitory impact on the rat aorta ring. As the amount of *Allium sativum* and melatonin rose, the inhibition rate dramatically increased, as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Dose-response curve of melatonin, *Allium sativum*, and their combination in the rat aortic rings model.

Table 1. Angiogenesis study in rats' aorta.

Concentration	Melatonin	<i>Allium sativum</i>	p-value
6.25 mcg	63.61 ± 3.709	38.60 ± 3.648	<0.001
12.5 mcg	76.74 ± 3.893	68.87 ± 2.457	<0.001
25 mcg	86.19 ± 6.074	80.71 ± 3.638	0.063
50 mcg	91.23 ± 4.990	87.50 ± 2.415	0.101
100 mcg	95.40 ± 2.506	93.20 ± 1.953	0.093

Data presented as mean ± standard deviation

Under the log (concentration) vs. normalized inhibition model, the IC₅₀ was calculated (IC₅₀ = 8.04 for *Allium sativum* and 3.313 for melatonin); see Fig. 1:

Melatonin and *Allium sativum* were each made in five different serial dilutions, and then those dilutions were administered to the embedded rat aortic rings to determine the dose-response curve. On the fifth day of the testing, both substances demonstrated substantial dose-dependent inhibition of the growth of blood vessels compared to the control group, which was treated with a one percent solution of DMSO. This finding was highly significant ($P < 0.001$). When assessing *Allium sativum* and melatonin, it was found

that at concentrations of 25 mcg and greater, there was no significant difference in the inhibitory effect on the rat aorta ring, supported by the data presented in Table 1 and Fig. 2.

On day 7 of the experiment, the zone of inhibition for each melatonin and *Allium sativum* sample was measured. The action of the extract caused the blood vessels in the CAM to begin to regress; the blood vessels had a disordered look and seemed pale yellow. The inhibition was identified as forming an avascular zone encircling the disc that contained the tested medications, and the degree of the inhibition zone was assessed using the scoring technique.

As shown in Table 2 and Fig. 5, the zone of inhibition for melatonin, *Allium sativum*, and the combination showed that the combination had the strongest effect on the CAM assay. This zone scored (++) and (+++), respectively.

Table 2. Assessment of zone of inhibition area (mm) for melatonin, *Allium sativum*, and their combination in the CAM assay.

Melatonin	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Combination
(3) +	(8) ++	(12) +++
(7) ++	(8) ++	(9) ++
(10) +++	(5) +	(12) +++
(13) +++	(12) +++	(7) ++
(9) ++	(6) ++	(10) +++
(3) +	(9) ++	(9) ++

Discussion

In the present investigation, melatonin was regarded as a positive control. When tested outside the body, the substance demonstrated a notable inhibitory effect on blood vessel formation in the rat aorta ring model. This effect depended on the dosage, and its significance was evident when compared to a negative control (DMSO). The IC₅₀ value was determined to be 3.313, and the behavior exhibited a sigmoidal curve.

The current study selected *Allium sativum* as the investigated medication to evaluate its possible anti-angiogenic capabilities. When administered at varying doses, the substance demonstrated a notable inhibitory effect on blood vessel formation in the rat aorta ring model. The impact of the substance was substantial when compared to the negative control (DMSO), with an IC₅₀ value of 8.04. Furthermore, its behavior exhibits a sigmoidal curve. Moreover, the synergistic impact of mixing both substances was seen, as indicated by a combination index ranging from 0 to 1 (Chou 2006).

The aortic ring assay allows for the ex vivo reproduction of important angiogenic processes, including endothelial migration, proliferation, proteolytic breakdown of the extracellular matrix, formation of capillary tubes, pericyte recruitment, and vascular regression (Aplin et al. 2008). The aortic ring angiogenic response is a multilevel-regulated, self-limiting process. Regarding the development, differentiation, and maintenance of blood vessels, paracrine and juxtacrine signaling between endothelial cells, fibroblasts, macrophages, and pericytes is indispensable (Nicosia and Villaschi 1995).

Our findings agreed with previous studies; in the Block et al. study, the authors reported significant

Figure 2. The dosage response effect was seen in the rat aortic rings model subjected to a series of *Allium sativum* concentrations. The following concentrations were tested: **A.** A negative control; **B.** 100 mcg/mL; **C.** 50 mcg/mL; **D.** 25 mcg/mL; **E.** 12.5 mcg/mL; and **F.** 6.25 mcg/mL. Note: the pointed black arrows indicate the growth of micro-blood vessels.

Figure 3. The dose-response effect of the *Allium sativum* and melatonin combination in the rat aortic rings model. **A.** Negative control; **B.** 50 mcg/mL *Allium sativum*; **C.** 50 mcg/mL combination. Note: the pointed black arrows indicate the growth of micro-blood vessels.

Figure 4. Assessment of the combination index (CI) at various concentrations for the *Allium sativum* and melatonin combination in the rat aortic rings model.

Figure 5. The degree of the inhibition zone of blood vessel growth in vivo (CAM) assay: **A.** Negative control (DMSO 1%); **B.** 50 mcg/mL *Allium sativum*; **C.** 50 mcg/mL melatonin, and **D.** Combination of 25 mcg/mL *Allium sativum* and 25 mcg/mL melatonin (50 mcg/mL).

anti-angiogenesis activity of several components of *Allium sativum*, which was examined by CAM assay (Block et al. 2017). *Allium sativum* stem extract was shown in another study to possess anti-angiogenic activity by inhibiting the expression of VEGF mRNA (Gam et al. 2021). Garlic components, such as diallyl trisulphide, diallyl sulfide, and alliin, have anti-angiogenic effects (Shukla et al. 2002; Mousa and Mousa 2005; Xiao et al. 2006), whereas aged garlic extract dose-dependently increases neovascularization in wound healing (Ejaz et al. 2009).

Since angiogenesis is a hallmark of various pathological conditions, it is essential for managing physiological processes like menstruation, wound healing, post-surgery tissue restoration, and stress recovery (Carmeliet 2003). A network of both stimulators and inhibitors delicately controls angiogenesis. An imbalance between these stimulators and inhibitors is believed to be the root cause of many diseases, including cancer, cardiovascular and neurological disorders, age-related macular degeneration, arthritis, psoriasis, obesity, and even asthma. Angiogenesis manipulation is a desirable and potentially effective treatment option for many pathological conditions (Li et al. 2022).

The present study's findings are novel since they investigate the previously unexplored anti-angiogenic properties of *Allium sativum* in an ex vivo rat aorta experiment. This strategy is commonly used as an efficient method to evaluate anti-angiogenic drugs in a complex system in-

volving interactions between endothelial cells, fibroblasts, pericytes, and smooth muscle cells.

Study limitations

The use of the rat ring aorta model has both advantages and disadvantages. One advantage is that it allows for the study of vessel outgrowth. However, a downside is the inconsistency in manipulating the rings and the potential impact of the quantity of surrounding tissue remaining on the vessel. Various rings from different aortas can also disrupt the angiogenic responses. Finally, the process of angiogenic vessel expansion takes place in three dimensions, making it challenging to capture and measure accurately with photography. When conducted with adequate internal controls and repeated numerous times, this assay is very uncomplicated, cost-effective, extremely informative, and notably superior to endothelium cultures in terms of its biological intricacy and significance.

Conclusions

The aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* provides a potent anti-angiogenesis effect, and its combination with melatonin had a synergistic effect, further enhancing its anti-angiogenesis effect.

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